

HISTORICAL SCIENCES

FRAGMENTS OF WOODEN BRIDGES OF THE MEDIEVAL CITY OF BELZ

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ABSTRACT

The materials of research carried out in the territory of Belz city center are published. During the work, two levels of wooden flooring of the 14th and 16th centuries were discovered. Their localization allowed to expand knowledge about the planning structure of the medieval city. The system of masonry beams and the nature of paving are traced. Analyzed mobile archaeological material discovered during research. A fragment of the wooden building of the city of the 15th century was explored. A fragment of brick construction from the 19th century, defined as the southern wall of the Palace of Rabbis, was localized. The stratigraphic layers dated back from the time of the existence of the roads to the period of the destruction of the palace was recorded. A significant number of fragments of late medieval ceramics and tiles were collected.

Keywords: wooden flooring, stratigraphy, construction, ceramic ware, Jewish Quarter, Palace of the Rabbis, market quarter.

Problem setting

During the study of the planning structure of medieval cities, the results of archeological research play an important role. Existing cartographic and written sources give a superficial idea of the nature of the building. When it comes to earlier periods of development of the city, in particular the late Middle Ages, this information is generally scarce. In this situation, archeological work comes to the fore. To a large extent this is facilitated by construction and restoration work, which is preceded by research on archeology. In this context, a preliminary study of two sites in the city of Belz was conducted.

The aim of the article is to highlight the new materials obtained as a result of archeological research on sites in the historical building of the city. To analyze the identified fixed objects and their impact on the structure of urban development.

Presentation of the material.

Belz is one of the oldest cities in Eastern Europe. The first written mention of the city dates back to 1030 [10, p. 19] is located on a low elevation among the marshy floodplain of the rivers Solokiya and Richytsi. Now it is a small town of Chervonohrad district, located 70 km north of the regional center – Lviv. The modern central part – the middle town, originated in the late 14th century with the provision of Magdeburg rights to the city. Over the past two decades, a number of archeological research has been carried out on its territory highlighted in the scientific literature. We will stop at two places where the remains of wooden roads and structures are found.

The first plot is located on the territory of the former Jewish district of the city. These works were related to the localization of the foundations of the rabbinical palace.

The history of Belz Jews begins in the 15th century. In the 16th century, the Belz townspeople allowed them to settle outside the city and build their synagogue. Since Belz did not belong to the cities where the

ban on the residence of Jews was in effect, it should be assumed that the Jewish quarter was formed in the northern part of the city center as early as the 15th-16th centuries. At the same time, mass Jewish construction began in Belz from the end of the 17th, especially from the 18th century [1, p. 157].

In 1570, there were already 20–25 Jewish families in Belz. Perhaps a wooden synagogue already existed at that time. In 1665, in connection with the city's decline, the Jewish population received equal rights with Roman Catholics and was allowed to buy houses in the city center. From then on, the weight of the Jewish population in Belz, which mainly settled in the northern part of the city center, was constantly growing. [2, p. 99]

At the end of the 19th century, a brick house was built on several purchased land plots – the so-called House of Rabbis with a Talmudic hall.

During World War I, the city was almost destroyed. During World War II and the first post-war decade, the construction of the Jewish Quarter was ruined. The only surviving monuments of Jewish culture in Belz are the former mikveh building and the cemetery in Lublin suburb [2, p. 108].

The location of the palace is recorded on cartographic materials: the cadastral plan from 1854 [5, map. 3.5] and the plan of the city made by A. Skarzhynski in 1916 [3, p. 124] where it is located in the southeastern part of the Jewish Quarter. We can also see the image of the building, particularly the facade, on interwar postcards [2, p. 107].

The first exploratory work on the search for the foundations of the palace was carried out in 2002 [9, p. 28]. Modern studies aimed to localize the southern wall of the Palace of the Rabbis. A 12×1 m trench was dug on the territory of the local school (Fig. 1) [7, c. 6]. In the process of deepening, a fragment of brick wall appeared in the northern part of the trench at a depth of 0.2 m. It was made of bricks measuring 29×15×6.5 cm on a strong lime-sand mortar of a yellowish color.

Figure 1 – Plan and stratigraphic profile of the excavated area

In the trench at a depth of 1,5 m, sandy layers significantly saturated with construction debris and mortar were recorded. The nature of their formation is most likely connected with the period of destruction of Jewish monuments in the middle of the 20th century.

During further works at a depth of 1,85 m in the southern part of the trench, wooden flooring was discovered. It consisted of one tier of logs with a width of up to 0,25 m. During fixation, a slight slope of the paving to the north was observed, which is also confirmed by the topography of an area. On an interval of four meters, the slope was 0,2 m. The wooden logs had an uneven surface and in some places were stacked on each other. Protruding knotty branches indicated the use of split logs. Dark gray sandy loam saturated with wood chips lay on top of the flooring. Fragments of 15th and 16th century ceramic ware were found in its infill.

In the northern part, the flooring was cut by the ruins of a wooden structure. The remains of an object consisted of randomly located boards, bars, and rounded piles of different diameters. At the western stratigraphic wall, the remains of a fallen fence, consisting of boards intertwined with wooden twigs, were traced. During the clearing of the ruins, fragments of ceramic ware from the 15th and 16th centuries were discovered. On the other hand, the ruins of the wooden building were cut by the brick wall of the Palace of the Rabbis. To preserve the wooden paving, further research was focused on the place of destruction of the wooden building. Under its ruins, loamy layers, significantly saturated with wood chips, and, in some places, solid layers of wood, were recorded.

At a depth of 3,2 m, another wooden flooring appeared. It was structurally similar to the upper one. Its characteristic feature was a slight shift of the direction (axis) relative to the upper one. A vertical pile with a diameter of 0,27 m, which probably belonged to the structure of the ruined building, was recorded directly on the paving. Movable archaeological material from

the level of the lower paving can be dated back to the late 14th and 15th centuries.

Limitations of the area of the research prevented us from establishing the width of the paving and tracing the number of layers from which it was constructed.

As a result of the research, a significant number of finds were collected in the trench. These are mainly fragments of pottery, which are represented by fragments of pot rims. The earliest among them are the rims profiled with a wide roller-shaped ledge, which forms a wide edge from the inside. This type of rims can be dated back to the second half of the 14th – 15th centuries. [4, p. 187]. Straight, slightly bent outward rims decorated with an ornament in the form of straight or wavy red lines were also discovered. The largest number is represented by rims bent outwards with a protruding edge in the middle. It should be noted that the rims decorated with painted ornaments are mainly made of white clay. A small percentage, among pots and bowls, are presented by rims decorated on the edge with an ornament in the form of a finger pinch.

Among other types of ware, a small number of bowls and lids were found. The latter are mainly represented by bulbs, among which an exemplar ornamented with a glazed, star-shaped pattern attracts attention.

Construction and decorative ceramics are mainly represented by tiles, among which the bank-shaped tile made of white clay should be noted. Similar finds have been repeatedly collected during other archaeological research in Belz. Chronologically, they belong to the 15th – 16th centuries. Both unglazed and covered with yellow-green glaze tiles with plant and anthropological ornaments were discovered.

Glass products are represented exclusively by fragments of vessels – the neck of a bottle, the bottom, and the stem of glasses. Among other finds, a ceramic pipe and a horseshoe attract attention.

In general, the discovered movable material can be dated back to the late 14th – 18th centuries.

As a result of the conducted research, it was possible to locate the southern wall of the Palace of the Rabbis, the location of which, when compared with previous works, gives a better idea of the parameters of the building.

The recorded two levels of wooden paving and the ruins of the building indicate an intensive and continuous development of the territory starting from the late 14th century without rejecting the possibility of starting the building in this area in an earlier period. During the work, it was not possible to trace the full picture of cultural layers, which should be the next task.

The second area of research is located directly at the market square. These works are connected with the

project of construction of shelter for elementary school [8, p. 9]. Analyzing cartographic materials, we see that the research area is located within the northern line of houses of the market square. It dates back to the end of the 14th century when the city was granted Magdeburg rights. It is clear that the construction of this time was wooden. According to historical sources, we know that there was a division of territory into parcels. In front of it there was a house, and behind it there was a courtyard and a number of buildings necessary for everyday life. It housed such premises as: Toilet, exit, water, furnaces, household facilities: stables, bread, storage rooms, separate benches.

Figure 2 – Wooden pavements in the Market Quarter

In the back part of the site was planned a fur-coat size 2x3 m. a significant part of the cultural layer, up to two meters, occupied monotonous layers of gray loam, which were accompanied by saturation of construction debris in the form of broken bricks, lumps of lime mortar and sand. In the middle of the stratigraphic column, at a depth of 0,75 m, a layer of light yellow sand was observed. Its power is not everywhere homogeneous, and on the western wall it is marked by a sharp decline to the north, repeating the terrain. Above the above layer, there was more saturation with broken brick with much larger fractions as opposed to the lower part. Such heterogeneity is associated with the consequences of historical processes in the studied area. Namely: after the destruction of the brick building market quarter after the first world war, the brick blocks were dismantled and moved north along the slope, which confirms the above-mentioned layer of sand. Only in the 50-s. in the 20th century, on the territory of the northern spicy market square, the building of the district party was built – the premises of the modern school.

In the future, in the northeast corner of the pit at a depth of 1,7 m, a horizontal lying wooden beam was

found that spoke from the western wall. It was characterized by a squish surface and shaking. On the northern and western stratigraphic wall, above the exposed beam, the contours of the trench were well read, which began at a depth of 0,6 m and ended at a mark of 1,9 m at the bottom of the contours were the remains of the scaffold wood, which could serve as walls. The upper part of the trench is cut as a result of leveling the site in the middle of the twentieth century. Based on the above signs, we can say that the south-east corner of the buried structure, which structurally had wooden walls, fell into the boundary of the pit. The location of the object in the depths of the parcelle indicates its economic purpose.

As a result of the fact that the cultural layer to a depth of 2 m was quite disturbed, the discovered moving material from this depth has a wide dating of the 15th – 18th centuries.

At a depth of two meters in the eastern part of the pit was a layer of white clay. The presence of the latter usually indicates a sterile layer which covered the remains of structures of destroyed structures, objects, etc.

The remains of the wooden structure in the form of horizontal beams were performed at a depth of 2,3 m in the western part of the pit. At the intersection, they were rounded up to 15 cm with a partially curved surface. The structures themselves covered a layer of white clay, which from a narrow lens in the western part of the pit increased to a power of 20 cm in the eastern part. Continuing clearing, a number of wooden beams with a flooring were opened for inspection. The upper tier of wooden structures is represented by three horizontal beams that are oriented along the north-south line. Their level of detection was in the range of depths of 2,22–2,34 m during the cleaning of the specified depth, fragments of ceramic dishes of the 16th century were found. The extreme east beam, in turn, lay on a wooden bed, which was available for a view of the width of 1,1 m its northern, eastern and southern edges went beyond the pit. It consisted of nine boards placed close to each other. Their surface – rough with knots and rather waterlogged. The thickness was from 1 to 3 cm with a width of up to 25 cm.

In the western part of the pit at a depth of 2,9 m there was another wooden flooring. In the available space for fixing there were five fragments of beams located close to each other. They are oriented by the ends on the east-west axis in a satisfactory state of conservation. Over the design, two fragments of ceramic tableware kin were found 14th-15th centuries.

Based on the fact that the entire area of the pit was occupied by wooden structures and the work is preventive in nature, research at this stage was discontinued.

In the course of the work, a small number of artifacts were discovered. Since the cultural layer on the site is almost completely disturbed, and the ceramic material was mainly in a postponed state, its dating has a wide chronological framework 14th – 18th centuries. According to the methodology developed in the archaeological literature, the discovered ceramic dishes can be divided by its use. So we refer to the kitchen utensils pots, tires, jars, macitres and pans, and to the table bowls, plates. Among the entire range of dishes dominated by kitchen ceramics.

Figure 3 – Ceramic (1-15) and metal (16, 17) finds from research

The earliest fragment is a smoothly bent outside crown of the pot, with a geometrically formed edge and a narrow furrow on the upper edge (Fig. 3, 2). According to the profile, it resembles ancient rus forms, but in the ceramic mass at the break there is no coarse-grained sand peculiar to ceramics of the princely era. So let's take him chronologically to the second part of 14th century. By the same time, we refer to another crown with a cornice profile, the lower part of which is decorated with small gorges (Fig. 3, 3). The surface of such a product has been angulated as evidenced by the remains on its surface.

The next century will be presented by the wreaths of the crown, decorated with a roller and a wide internal edge (Fig. 3, 13). The surface has a gray, sometimes light gray shade. Pots of this period have numerous analogies and are often found in the study of medieval cities.

By the 16th century, we include fragments of the crown pots, which are almost the same type. They are characterized by a loosened outside profile with a pronounced, sometimes sharp undercrowned edge, and differ from each other by different modeling edge (Fig. 3, 6, 8). There are crowns with cut, cut to the middle or granular edge. Often they are decorated with rubble on the edge or decorated with painted stripes of red color.

The next period of the 16th – 17th centuries is represented by fragments of pots with a wavy profile of a crown, which are slightly deflected outside and have a roller-shaped ledge on the outside. The edge of the crown is rounded, often thickened (Fig. 3, 14). They are often covered with watering and decorated with various ornaments.

To large forms of dishes count two fragments of macitre. They are represented by massive sharply deviated crowns with thickened edges. The diameter of the crown was measured only in one fragment, which is more than 30 cm, and refers to the largest forms that are characteristic of later times – the 17th century. Also, the inner part of this fragment is decorated with a painted ornament with red paint. According to the scientific literature, the use of red paint for ornamentation falls on the second half of the 16th – first half 17th century. Comparing these criteria, we give fragments of the macitres of the 17th century.

Pitchers. This category of dishes represents a piece of a wreath with a wavy profile and a roller-shaped projection from the outside. Although the fragment was found at considerable depth and accompanied by fragments of ceramic dishes of the earlier centuries, the character of the profile indicates a later date of this form, namely the 17th – 18th centuries.

Bowls are represented by several finds that are characterized by conical forms of the trunk, which abruptly turns into a straight crown. The edges of the crown are rounded slightly thickened. The same products of gray color are sometimes decorated from the middle with a tickled ornament. According to the chronology, we refer them to the 17th – 18th centuries.

The pen and a small fragment of the form itself are included in the pans. The discovered handle of tubular shape is made of white kaolin clay. Its edge is barely swinging like a bottle neck. On the other side there is a

fragment of the sidewall, which in turn is covered with yellow-green irrigation. As for the detected form, the reconstruction can determine that it had a small, mica-shaped trunk with a diameter of 14 cm, which is covered from the middle with green irrigation and is decorated with corrugated outside. The crown is roller-shaped with a wide edge under the tire. The preserved leg is made of a roller of clay and is honed to the desired oval section. It should be noted its relatively high height – 6 cm. A similar shape of the crown and other indicated signs of the detected frying pan indicate the use of this type in the 15th century.

Tires. All three copies are presented with handles-grasp. Therefore, it is impossible to reconstruct the original form of the whole form. The covers of these covers have a round button-shaped shape with perpendicular and oblique edge, with one of them being quite burned. Due to the wide distribution of the button-shaped cover grip, it is difficult to sell these products more accurately based only on this element. We are still dating them in the 16th century.

To the rare types of dishes include a fragment of the form for baking. The preserved part is made of kaolin clay and partly covered with green irrigation. At the intersection it is oval with horizontally cut edges. Fragmentation of the find does not allow us to talk about certain parameters. However, similar forms were found in Lviv and in many cities of Poland [11, p. 283]. They are characterized by an elongated tube-shaped shape with a massive belt handle that is attached externally to the body. The placement of the handle is both horizontal and vertical in relation to the shape. This type of cookware was used for baking and frying meat dishes. The second half of the 16th century.

Finds related to building ceramics are presented only by tiles. Typologically, this is a cast tile decorated with low relief ornament with a floral and geometric motif. All fragments are covered with green irrigation and date back to the 17th century.

Glass products are represented by a small group of finds and consist of fragments of bottles, glasses and pens of glasses. Two bottle necks are found that are made of thick transparent and green glass, so it is quite difficult to talk about their shape. The first is characterized by a narrow-throat shape with smoothly bent edges, the other – a straight neck with horizontally loosened edges of the crown. With a small thickness of glass, we can assume that the discovered necks belong to small bottles. Typologically, such finds have a wide use in the modern period. So chronologically we refer them to the 17th – 18th centuries.

Two lower parts of these vessels are counted to the glasses. The first is a round-shaped bell-shaped ring-shaped leg with the bottom and remains of pontius concave to the middle. The surface of the product is highly patinated. This type of glasses was widely distributed in the 17th – 18th centuries throughout the Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth [13, p. 251]. The second is a cylindrical glass bottom made of light, slightly greenish glass mass. Rounded shape with a cone-shaped concave bottom and remains of pontius. Decorate along the edge with plastic jaws. This type of glasses also had a wide use and chronologically does not differ with the above.

The least in the number of metal products detected, it is a nail and spur. Nail – forged, rectangular in the intersection with a rectangular, elongated barely oval top cap. According to the developed typology, this product belongs to the group R1b, which is defined as coffin nails and dates from the 17th – 18th centuries [12, p. 68].

Spur. From the cultural layer comes a metal spur with U – a similar bracket with ring completion and a wheel (Fig. 3, 16). The state of conservation of the wheel is quite poor, which makes it impossible to calculate the exact amount of its rays (according to the reconstruction, it can be assumed that there were 6 of them). The discovered spur according to the developed typologies refers to late forms and had a wide use from the 13th century to the end of the 15th century [6, p. 122].

According to the results of the work, a fragment of the back part of the parcelle with the object of the 18th century and two wooden decking of the end of the 14th – 16th centuries was found. As you can see from the fixation in the upper and lower onstyle, the direction of the location of the beams is preserved. This shows that the direction of movement passed from south to north, that is, from the market square. It should be noted that the dating of the detected bridge is laid during the first and second location of the city.

Conclusions and suggestions

Summing up the research, we can state that during the archeological work we managed to find two locations of wooden roads in the middle of the city of Belz. After analyzing the detected findings from the objects, we can divide the detected road levels into two periods. The lower levels of the flooring in both cases date back to the end of the 14th – 15th century, which corresponds to the time of the first location of the city after the granting of Magdeburg rights in 1377. During the 15th century, the city experienced severe events such as fires and devastating attacks by enemies. This led to a certain decline in the city and a partial loss of road function. The reflection of this is observed in the layers that formed on top of the lower deck. The difference between the two bridge was from 0,5 m to 1,2 m. The upper level of the road dates back to the 16th century, and this is the period of the second location of the city after the restoration of the right of self-government, which took place in 1509 as we see the network of city roads was restored in the same directions and axes as the previous ones.

The discovery of wooden flooring in the market quarter suggests that the planning structure of houses on the market was different in nature than we can see on the first maps of the city. It is likely that in some places between the houses there were lanes on one of which they managed to stumble upon. For example, we

note that a similar situation has been observed more than once in Lviv. Here, in the course of archaeological research, stone paving of lanes that existed between houses and were lost as a result of perestroika after a fire in the 16th century. The question of whether the planning of the market square in Belz differed during the first and second locations may be answered by the following studies.

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